

Primer: Dynamic Reporting

Felix Hofmann, Samuel Pawel, Monika Hebeisen, Leonhard Held
doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7565735](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7565735)

What is dynamic reporting?

Dynamic reporting goes back to a paradigm called *literate programming* which was developed by Knuth (1984) for computer programming. At the time, software engineers were faced with the problem that their source code was not easily understandable for other people such as collaborators or clients. Literate programming solves this problem by combining the machine-readable source code and its human-readable documentation into one document.

As science became more quantitative and computer-dependent, researchers quickly recognized the importance of literate programming for writing dynamic research reports. Modern dynamic reporting systems allow researchers to perform data analysis and to write the corresponding documentation in a single document, making each step easier to understand, automating boring and error-prone tasks, and improving computational reproducibility.

Why should I use dynamic reporting?

In many empirical research disciplines, writing scientific analyses starts with importing a data set into a software tool and executing specific commands in order to get the desired numerical results, tables and figures, as illustrated in Figure 1 (top). This output is subsequently copied and pasted manually into a typesetting program, the results are discussed and the scientific report is finalized (Xie, 2015). This two-step procedure has various disadvantages:

- Use of two separate software tools for analysing and reporting is awkward and tedious
- Many manual steps make the approach prone to errors and not directly reproducible
- Updates in the original data set require the whole manual process to be repeated
- Sharing the full analysis and reporting pipeline with other researchers is difficult
- Reusing the analysis procedure on similar problems is cumbersome

Dynamic reporting addresses these issues through a combination of analysis code and text in one document. As such the analysis and the reporting are integrated in one software environment as illustrated in Figure 1 (bottom).

How do I use dynamic reporting?

There are various implementations of dynamic reporting, the most popular ones are R Markdown (Xie et al., 2018) and Jupyter Notebooks (Kluyver et al., 2016). Both of them combine the simple Markdown syntax to specify text and layout with commonly used programming languages (e.g., R, Python, and Julia), and are therefore easy to learn for beginners. Recently, a more modern implementation named Quarto was introduced by the developers of R Markdown. Quarto works with R, Python and Julia, and is quickly gaining popularity. Other implementations (e.g., knitr, Sweave, pweave, and weave.jl) use LaTeX instead of Markdown, a more powerful but also more difficult typesetting system. These implementations are therefore intended for more advanced users. Some commercial programs (e.g., Mathematica or MATLAB) also offer implementations of dynamic reporting but are not very popular because they are inaccessible to people without a license. There are also online platforms for sharing

Manual reporting

Dynamic reporting

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of manual reporting (top) and dynamic reporting (bottom) workflows.

and collaboratively working on dynamic reports in the cloud, for instance, Binder (Jupyter et al., 2018) and Google Colab.

We recommend R Markdown (for R) and Jupyter Notebooks (for Python and Julia) to beginners who want to learn dynamic reporting. Both are powerful, free and open-source, and easy to use. In the following, we will briefly explain the basics of R Markdown and Jupyter Notebook.

R Markdown

Dynamic reporting with R Markdown is done via R Markdown files which have the file extension .Rmd. These files can be edited in any text editor. Figure 2 shows an R Markdown file opened in the RStudio editor. RStudio is not required for using R Markdown but we recommend it for beginners since it makes using R Markdown much easier.

The image shows two side-by-side windows. The left window is RStudio, displaying an R Markdown file named 'report.Rmd'. The right window is a Chromium browser showing the rendered HTML output of the R Markdown file.

RStudio (Left):

```

1 ---
2 title: "Report: Analysis of names from newborn children in Zurich"
3 author: "Felix Hofmann, Samuel Pawel"
4 date: "30 November 2022"
5 output: html_document
6 ---
7
8 ```{r "setup", include = FALSE}
9 ## this is the R chunk to specify the options
10 knitr::opts_chunk$set(echo = TRUE, # display R code
11                       warning = FALSE, # don't display warning messages
12                       message = FALSE, # don't display package loading messages
13                       fig.align = "center", # center figures
14                       out.width = "100%" # figures fill entire width
15                       )
16 ---
17
18 In this document we will give an example of dynamic reporting using a data set containing the names of
19 newborn children in the city of Zurich since the year 1993. The data were downloaded from
20 <https://data.stadt-zuerich.ch/dataset/bev_vornamen_baby_od3700>.
21
22 ## Import data and perform manipulations
23
24 We will now import the data and perform some manipulations, such as rename the variables into English and
25 computing the most common name by year and sex.
26
27 ```{r "data"}
28 ## load data
29 dat <- read.csv(file = "../data/namesZurich.csv")
30
31 ## data manipulations
32 library(dplyr)
33 datCleaned <- dat %>%
34   rename(year = StichtagDatJahr,
35          name = Vorname,
36          sex = SexLang,
37          births = AnzGebuWir) %>%
38   group_by(year, sex) %>%
39   top_n(n = 1, wt = births)
40
41 Last year, the most common male name was `r filter(datCleaned, year == 2021, sex == "männlich")$name` whereas
42 the most common female name was `r filter(datCleaned, year == 2021, sex == "weiblich")$name`.
  
```

Chromium Browser (Right):

Report: Analysis of names from newborn children in Zurich

Felix Hofmann, Samuel Pawel
30 November 2022

In this document we will give an example of dynamic reporting using a data set containing the names of newborn children in the city of Zurich since the year 1993. The data were downloaded from https://data.stadt-zuerich.ch/dataset/bev_vornamen_baby_od3700.

Import data and perform manipulations

We will now import the data and perform some manipulations, such as rename the variables into English and computing the most common name by year and sex.

```

## load data
dat <- read.csv(file = "../data/namesZurich.csv")

## data manipulations
library(dplyr)
datCleaned <- dat %>%
  rename(year = StichtagDatJahr,
         name = Vorname,
         sex = SexLang,
         births = AnzGebuWir) %>%
  group_by(year, sex) %>%
  top_n(n = 1, wt = births)
  
```

Last year, the most common male name was Noah whereas the most common female name was Olivia.

Data visualization

We will now visualize the most common name by year and sex.

```

library(ggplot2)
ggplot(data = datCleaned, aes(x = year, y = births, color = sex)) +
  geom_line(aes(group = name), alpha = 0.3, show.legend = FALSE) +
  geom_label(aes(label = name), alpha = 0.8, show.legend = FALSE, size = 2) +
  scale_color_brewer(palette = "Dark2") +
  
```

Figure 2: Example of an R Markdown file opened in RStudio (left) and its HTML output (right).

report.ipynb - JupyterLab - Chromium

localhost:8888/lab/tree/report.ipynb

File Edit View Run Kernel Tabs Settings Help

report.ipynb Python 3 (ipykernel)

Introduction

Jupyter Notebook documents contain two types of cells. This cell, for example, contains text that can be formatted using markdown syntax (see [here](#) for a guide) whereas the other type of cells contains code that can be run by a Python, R, or Julia kernel. In order to showcase the capabilities of a Jupyter Notebook with respect to dynamic reporting, the following cells import a data set which contains the names of newborn children in the city of Zurich since 1993. The data set is published by the city of Zurich and can be downloaded under this [link](#).

Loading Python modules

The next cell is the first cell that, in this case, contains Python code. It imports the necessary modules such that we can run this small example analysis.

```
[1]: import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

Importing and manipulating the data

Now that this is done, we can import the data set and perform the desired operations on it. Here, we will first rename the columns of the data frame and then find the most common name(s) for each gender and year.

```
[2]: # Import data set
dat = pd.read_csv("../data/namesZurich.csv")

# Rename the columns
dat.rename(columns = {"StichtagDatJahr": "year", "Vorname": "name",
                    "SexLang": "sex", "AnzGebuWir": "births"}, inplace = True)

# Replace sex by english expressions
dat["sex"] = np.where(dat["sex"] == "männlich", "male", "female")

# Get the most common name(s) per year and sex
idx = dat.groupby(["year", "sex"])["births"].transform(max) == dat["births"]
datClean = dat[idx].sort_values(["year", "sex"]).reset_index(drop = True)
```

```
[3]: datClean
```

	year	name	sex	births
0	1993	Laura	female	31

Simple 1 Python 3 (ipykernel) | Idle Mode: Command Ln 1, Col 1 report.ipynb

report.pdf 61.7%

Analysis of names from newborn children in Zurich

Felix Hofmann, Samuel Pawel

November 30, 2022

1 Introduction

Jupyter Notebook documents contain two types of cells. This cell, for example, contains text that can be formatted using markdown syntax (see [here](#) for a guide) whereas the other type of cells contains code that can be run by a Python, R, or Julia kernel. In order to showcase the capabilities of a Jupyter Notebook with respect to dynamic reporting, the following cells import a data set which contains the names of newborn children in the city of Zurich since 1993. The data set is published by the city of Zurich and can be downloaded under this [link](#).

2 Loading Python modules

The next cell is the first cell that, in this case, contains Python code. It imports the necessary modules such that we can run this small example analysis.

```
[1]: import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

3 Importing and manipulating the data

Now that this is done, we can import the data set and perform the desired operations on it. Here, we will first rename the columns of the data frame and then find the most common name(s) for each gender and year.

```
[2]: # Import data set
dat = pd.read_csv("../data/namesZurich.csv")

# Rename the columns
dat.rename(columns = {"StichtagDatJahr": "year", "Vorname": "name",
                    "SexLang": "sex", "AnzGebuWir": "births"}, inplace = True)

# Replace sex by english expressions
dat["sex"] = np.where(dat["sex"] == "männlich", "male", "female")
```

Figure 3: Example of a Jupyter Notebook opened in JupyterLab (left) and its pdf output (right).

Every R Markdown file starts with a header code block enclosed by three hyphens (---) where meta data and the output is specified.¹ In our example, we choose `html` as output format, however, many other types are possible (for example `pdf` or `docx`). After the file header, the main part of the R Markdown file starts. Text can now be written in the usual Markdown syntax. For example, `*text*` becomes *text*, `**text**` becomes **text**, or `#section` and `##subsection` become headings (the official syntax is documented here <http://daringfireball.net/projects/markdown/syntax>, see also [Ovadia, 2014](#)). Between passages of text, it is possible to embed R and/or Python code in so-called *code chunks* that start with ```{r}` or ```{python}`, respectively, and end with ````.² Figures are automatically inserted in the output. Function, such as `kable` from the `knitr` package or `xtable` from the `xtable` package ([Dahl et al., 2019](#)) can be used for dynamically generating tables. R code can also be placed inline, i.e. embedded in text sentences. This is useful for reporting analysis results, such as effect sizes or confidence intervals, automatically in the text. An inline R code chunk starts with ``r` and ends with ```. By clicking on the “knit” button in RStudio the `Rmd` source file is converted to the specified output format.³ For an R Markdown file to compile successfully, it is required that the code in the `Rmd` file runs successfully without errors. This can be seen as a further advantage of dynamic reporting with R Markdown as it ensures a minimum degree of error-free code.

Jupyter Notebooks

Dynamic reporting with Jupyter Notebooks is based on iPython notebook `ipynb` files. These files are typically edited in the Jupyter Notebook or the JupyterLab browser interface. JupyterLab is more modern and has more features but both essentially link a notebook editor with an interactive session of a specific programming language like Python, R, or Julia. An advantage of this design is that the browser serves as a file editor which provides simple access to all of the built-in functionality. In general, working with Jupyter Notebooks offers much more of a point-and-click experience than editing R Markdown files which allows beginners to be productive from the beginning. This can be seen in [Figure 3](#) (left), which shows an example notebook opened in JupyterLab. However, due to the simple user interface, Jupyter Notebooks are also a bit limited when it comes to the layout of the output document. In terms of supported output formats, Jupyter Notebooks offer a wide variety of options to export a Notebook as `html`, `tex`, `md`, `pdf`, and other file formats. [Figure 3](#) (right) shows the notebook exported to a `pdf` document.

Want to learn more?

The code from the examples above is available at <https://github.com/crsuzh/dynamicReporting>. The repository also includes `knitr` and Quarto versions of the same examples. More about R Markdown can be learned in the online book by [Xie et al. \(2018\)](#). There is also an excellent book on `knitr` ([Xie, 2015](#)) with comprehensive online documentation (<https://yihui.org/knitr/>). The Turing Way handbook to reproducible, ethical and collaborative data science ([Turing Way Community et al., 2019](#)) provides further information on dynamic reporting with Jupyter notebooks and other tools for reproducible research. [Peikert and Brandmaier \(2021\)](#) explain how dynamic reporting can be combined with other computational tools such as containerization, version control, and dependency management. Hands-on tutorials for dynamic reporting are given in the online courses “[Reproducible Research using Jupyter Notebooks](#)” ([Data Carpentry, 2016](#)) and “[R for Reproducible Scientific Analysis](#)” ([Zimmerman et al., 2019](#)) by the software/data carpentry, and the [R Markdown tutorial](#) ([RStudio, 2020](#)) from RStudio.

¹The header code block is also called the YAML header because the YAML configuration language is used within.

²For more details on the Python integration in R Markdown see the `reticulate` cheat sheet ([RStudio, 2019](#)).

³Internally, RStudio runs the function `rmarkdown::render`, so if RStudio is not used this functions needs to be called instead.

Acknowledgments

We thank Ulrike Held, Eva Furrer, and Rachel Heyard for helpful comments and access to their teaching materials.

References

- Dahl, D. B., Scott, D., Roosen, C., Magnusson, A., and Swinton, J. (2019). *xtable: Export Tables to LaTeX or HTML*. URL <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=xtable>. R package version 1.8-4.
- Data Carpentry (2016). Reproducible Research using Jupyter Notebooks. URL <https://reproducible-science-curriculum.github.io/workshop-RR-Jupyter/>.
- Jupyter, P., Bussonnier, M., Forde, J., Freeman, J., Granger, B., Head, T., Holdgraf, C., Kelley, K., Nalvarte, G., Osheroff, A., Pacer, M., Panda, Y., Perez, F., Ragan-Kelley, B., and Willing, C. (2018). Binder 2.0 – reproducible, interactive, sharable environments for science at scale. doi:[10.25080/majora-4af1f417-011](https://doi.org/10.25080/majora-4af1f417-011).
- Kluyver, T., Ragan-Kelley, B., Pérez, F., Granger, B. E., Bussonnier, M., Frederic, J., Kelley, K., Hamrick, J. B., Grout, J., Corlay, S., et al. (2016). *Jupyter Notebooks – a publishing format for reproducible computational workflows*, volume 2016. doi:[10.3233/978-1-61499-649-1-87](https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-649-1-87).
- Knuth, D. E. (1984). Literate Programming. *The Computer Journal*, 27(2):97–111. doi:[10.1093/comjnl/27.2.97](https://doi.org/10.1093/comjnl/27.2.97).
- Ovadia, S. (2014). Markdown for librarians and academics. *Behavioral & Social Sciences Librarian*, 33(2):120–124. doi:[10.1080/01639269.2014.904696](https://doi.org/10.1080/01639269.2014.904696).
- Peikert, A. and Brandmaier, A. M. (2021). A reproducible data analysis workflow. *Quantitative and Computational Methods in Behavioral Sciences*, 1. doi:[10.5964/qcmb.3763](https://doi.org/10.5964/qcmb.3763).
- RStudio (2019). Use Python with R with reticulate. URL https://ugoproto.github.io/ugo_r_doc/pdf/reticulate.pdf.
- RStudio (2020). R Markdown from RStudio: Introduction. URL <https://rmarkdown.rstudio.com/lesson-1.html>.
- Turing Way Community, Arnold, B., Bowler, L., Gibson, S., Herterich, P., Higman, R., Krystalli, A., Morley, A., O'Reilly, M., and Whitaker, K. (2019). *The Turing Way: A Handbook for Reproducible Data Science*. Zenodo. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.3233986](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3233986).
- Xie, Y. (2015). *Dynamic Documents with R and knitr*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL.
- Xie, Y., Allaire, J. J., and Golemund, G. (2018). *R markdown: The definitive guide*. Chapman and Hall/CRC. URL <https://bookdown.org/yihui/rmarkdown/>.
- Zimmerman, N., Wilson, G., Silva, R., Ritchie, S., Michonneau, F., Oliver, J., Dashnow, H., Boughton, A., Teucher, A., et al. (2019). swcarpentry/r-novice-gapminder: Software Carpentry: R for Reproducible Scientific Analysis, June 2019. doi:[10.5281/zenodo.3265164](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3265164).

Version from September 18, 2023.

This work is published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license ([CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)).

Edited by Felix Hofmann ([0000-0002-3891-6239](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3891-6239)), Samuel Pawel ([0000-0003-2779-320X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2779-320X)), and Leonhard Held ([0000-0002-8686-5325](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8686-5325)).